

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D4.2 EX-POST EVALUATION OF BUSINESS MODELS FOR IMPROVING SOIL HEALTH IN AGRICULTURE

Ex-post evaluation of business models for improving soil health in agriculture

Summary

This report evaluates soil health business models in Swiss arable farming as part of the InBestSoil project. Drawing on a 2023/24 nationwide survey of 2,728 farms and econometric modelling, it assesses the effects of soil management practices on farm productivity and sustainability. The analysis is framed within a soil-health-based sustainable business model framework, specifically Archetype 6: Facilitate Sustainability Transition, which operationalises how farms can shift toward more sustainable models while accounting for behavioural and structural factors.

Three core findings emerge. First, a productivity-soil health trade-off exists: intensive management boosts short-term yields but degrades soils over time. Second, a market failure prevails, as farmers rationally prioritise private returns while public benefits — carbon storage, biodiversity — remain undervalued. Third, experience and farm scale matter significantly, with larger, more experienced operations better positioned to adopt sustainable practices efficiently.

Methodologically, the study introduces an Arable Soil Management Index (based on the universal soil loss equation) fed into a stochastic frontier analysis to estimate yield and efficiency impacts. A practical output is a digital benchmarking app enabling farmers to compare their practices with peers and receive tailored guidance.

The report concludes that policy must correct the market failure through instruments such as payments for ecosystem services and performance-based schemes, embedding soil health into both business and governance frameworks in support of the EU Mission Soil objectives.

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Executive Summary

The D4.2 report presents the ex-post evaluation of business models and soil management practices that aim to improve soil health in Swiss agriculture, as part of Work Package 4, Task 2 of the InBestSoil project and in relation to the second Living Lab of the project. The analysis draws on an extensive national survey of arable farms and detailed empirical estimation of production functions. The Swiss case is positioned within the broader soil-health-based sustainable business model framework developed in Deliverable 4.1. The findings of this ex-post evaluation can, in particular, be interpreted through Archetype 6: Facilitate Sustainability Transition. It operationalises the archetype and sheds light on the behavioural aspects of business model adoption and resulting impacts. The report is relevant for policymakers at the national and EU level designing agri-environmental schemes, land-use planners and environmental managers concerned with soil conservation, farmer organisations and advisory services seeking evidence on soil practices, and researchers in agricultural economics and sustainability science.

A nationwide survey in 2023/24 collected 2,728 farm responses, capturing structural, behavioural, and attitudinal factors influencing soil management. A new **Arable Soil Management Index**, based on the universal soil loss equation, quantified soil-friendly practices. This index was used in a **stochastic frontier analysis** of wheat production, corrected for self-selection bias, to estimate impacts on yields, efficiency, and input use.

The analysis leads to three key messages: (1) a trade-off between productivity and soil health exists in that intensive management improves short-term yields and efficiency but degrades soils; (2) a market failure prevails, as farmers prioritise private returns, leaving public benefits like carbon storage and biodiversity undervalued; (3) the role of experience and scale matter, since more experienced managers and larger farms are more efficient, showing the importance of skills and scale for sustainable adoption.

The deliverable results demonstrate the value of combining behavioural surveys with econometric modelling to capture farm decision-making. For practice, the project's benchmarking app allows farmers to compare their soil practices with peers and supports advisory services in promoting gradual adoption of sustainable practices.

The findings provide evidence for policy and advisory frameworks that support soil protection, reinforcing InBestSoil's goal of embedding soil health in business and governance. Policies must address the market failure by creating incentives that reward long-term soil health, such as payments for ecosystem services and performance-based schemes. Findings are directly relevant to Mission Soil objectives on reducing degradation, increasing soil organic matter, and enhancing monitoring.

This deliverable confirms that soil-friendly practices are essential for reconciling farm productivity with long-term sustainability. It is structured as follows:

Chapter 1: Background introduces the survey methodology and contextualises it within the broader Swiss agricultural sector. The country-wide online survey, conducted in winter 2023/24, targeted over 15,000 eligible arable farms and yielded 2,728 complete responses—a robust sample representing the diversity of Swiss arable farming. The chapter outlines Switzerland's agricultural structure, its distinct policy and payment schemes that support soil health, and the distinction between public and private initiatives. The survey was designed to capture not only practice adoption but also behavioural, structural, and attitudinal factors influencing farmers' decisions. It also covers the input and output parameters for the most important arable crop, which is winter wheat.

Chapter 2: The impact analysis is based on a detailed conceptual and empirical framework used to assess how soil health practices influence farm productivity and efficiency, particularly in milling wheat production.

Recognising that farmers often adopt bundles of practices rather than isolated measures, this chapter introduces a novel Arable Soil Management Index based on the universal soil loss equation (C-factor). This index then enters the estimation of a production function. A stochastic frontier analysis (SFA), corrected for endogeneity, quantifies the impact of varied soil management strategies on output and input use. The analysis finds that, when taking into account endogeneity, a greater intensity of soil management leads to higher productivity and greater input efficiency, whilst such intense management is negative for soil health.

Chapter 3: The project's dissemination activities are described to understand the outreach and engagement efforts. A key outcome was the development of a digital benchmarking app, which allowed participating farmers to compare their soil management practices with peers and access tailored recommendations. This tool was positively received and presented to Swiss federal agricultural authorities. Additional dissemination included presentations at policy forums, academic conferences, and a forthcoming publication.

Overall, deliverable 4.2 offers a comprehensive dataset and analytical approach to evaluate the real-world impact of soil health practices in arable farming. It contributes valuable evidence for designing more effective and targeted incentives to promote sustainable land management, while also highlighting the complex interplay between policy, behaviour, and agronomic outcomes in Swiss agriculture, with wider relevance to soil health promotion across arable farms in Central Europe.

Chapter 1 – Background

We begin with a brief introduction to the survey that was conducted, followed by an overview of the Swiss farming sector, the study area, and the relevant payment schemes. Subsequently, this chapter outlines the survey design, the procedures applied, and the sources of both primary and secondary data. Finally, it includes a note on open data publication and data accessibility. In terms of business model analysis, we focus on Archetype 6 from Deliverable D4.1: Facilitate Sustainability Transition. This archetype emphasizes the role of supportive policies, collaborative arrangements, and macro-level incentives in enabling farmers to adopt soil health practices and transition toward more sustainable agricultural systems. It highlights value creation through stakeholder engagement, policy support, and coordinated initiatives, with value capture emerging from incentives, recognition, and long-term environmental benefits.

1.1 Setting

To assess current soil health interventions across Switzerland, we conducted an online survey focused on identifying soil management practices on arable farms. Initially, the survey targeted only farms participating in a carbon farming initiative in the canton of Basel-Landschaft, as well as non-participating farms within the same canton. Nevertheless, the scope of the survey was increased to encompass the wider adoption of soil management practices, aligned with the principles of soil health and carbon sequestration, across the whole country. The survey focused on arable farming practices during the 2022/2023 growing season, with a particular emphasis on soil health and conservation measures. Farms were selected based on clearly defined eligibility criteria to ensure the dataset accurately represents the conditions of arable production in Switzerland. These criteria aimed to include farms with a strong emphasis on arable cropping, which was essential for analysing soil management strategies. To be eligible, farms had to meet the following conditions:

- Grow wheat in the preceding season (2021/2022).
- Farm at least 3 hectares of arable land in the preceding season (2021/2022).
- Arable land must have comprised at least 20% of the total farmed area in the preceding season (2021/2022).

In August 2023, we received contact details for 15'023 eligible farmers from the Federal Office for Agriculture (FOAG) for the purpose of conducting the survey. This group represents approximately 31% of all farms in Switzerland and includes around 95% of all arable farms nationwide. The dataset provided by FOAG included email addresses, farm ID numbers, preferred language, as well as names and titles.

Before presenting the data collection protocol and the detailed variables of the datasets, we first provide a brief introduction to the study area and associated policy background in Switzerland at the time of our study.

1.2 Swiss agricultural sector

Farmers' soil health practices do not occur in isolation but are embedded in specific characteristics of Swiss agriculture. Therefore, understanding the main features of the Swiss agricultural sector is crucial for contextualising the survey results.

In 2023, Switzerland's agricultural sector encompassed 47,719 farm enterprises, each covering an average farm size of 21.84 hectares (FSO, 2024). Nationally, arable land accounted for a total of 274,896.24 hectares. Among

the cultivated crops, winter wheat represented the largest share, covering 78,075.96 hectares (28.40% of the arable land) (FSO, 2025a) and amounting to a total inland production of 413'805 tonnes in 2023 (80.63% going to human consumption) (FSO, 2024). The sector employed 148,880 individuals, 44.21% on a permanent basis in 2023. 71.03% of all farms were considered full-time enterprises (FSO, 2024).

The sector is structured around three main production systems: conventional farming, integrated production (IP-Suisse), and organic farming. Conventional farming remains the dominant system in terms of land use and farm numbers. Followed by Integrated production (IP), which is a state-recognised system that emphasizes resource efficiency, soil protection, and reduced – but not eliminated – use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers (IP Suisse, 2025). And finally the organic farming production system, that adheres to even stricter standards, entirely banning both synthetic pesticides and herbicides (FSO, 2025b).

Economic trade-offs between the production systems are evident in yield and price structures. In winter wheat production, conventional farms achieve the highest average yields at 7.07 tonnes/ha, followed by IP-Suisse with 5.56 tonnes/ha, and organic systems with 4.55 tonnes/ha. Prices, however, reflect the additional environmental efforts: in 2023, conventional milling wheat sold for 585 CHF/tonne, IP-Suisse wheat received a 50 CHF/tonne premium, and organic wheat fetched up to 1,075 CHF/tonne (Agridea, 2024). Furthermore, both IP-Suisse and organic producers can access additional payments of 400 CHF/ha for refraining from plant protection products, 250 CHF/ha for avoiding herbicides, and up to 1,200 CHF/ha for organic arable farming under designated ecological incentive schemes.

The agricultural sector is shaped not only by a diverse production landscape, but also by the topography. Figure 1 illustrates the delineation of Switzerland's varied topography with the different agricultural zones, which account for the varying production conditions across the country. These zones help to ensure that the challenges faced by farmers in different regions are appropriately considered in the application of agricultural policies. For instance, the mountain zones are characterized by steep slopes and shorter vegetation periods, while the valley and hill zones offer more favourable conditions for farming. The majority of Switzerland's arable farms are located in the valley and hill zones.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of agricultural zones in Switzerland. Arable farms are mainly situated in valley and hill zones. The classification is based on data provided by the Federal Office for Agriculture of Switzerland.

Climatic patterns across Switzerland are strongly influenced by elevation and geography. Therefore, apart from the agricultural zones, Switzerland can also be divided into several biographical zones (Figure 2). These regions are particularly relevant for understanding the diversity of agricultural systems. The biographical regions are shaped by a complex interplay of environmental characteristics, including topography, climate patterns, and soil properties, which together influence land use strategies, and the types of crops cultivated. The Jura Mountains can be found in the northwest; the central Swiss Plateau and the Alpine region are stretching across the south and east of the country. Arable crop production is predominantly located within the Swiss Plateau, where flatter terrain and more favourable climatic conditions support intensive cultivation (FSO, 2024). The Plateau generally experiences a continental climate, characterised by cold winters and warm summers. Additional details on national climatic conditions can be found on the MeteoSwiss website: [The climate of Switzerland - MeteoSwiss](#).

Beyond physical geography, Switzerland's agricultural landscape is also embedded within a special cultural context defined by four official language regions—German, French, Italian, and Romansh (Figure 2). The boundaries of these linguistic regions are not only culturally significant but can also influence regional differences in agricultural practices, knowledge exchange, and policy implementation. Language, in this context, intersects with social networks, advisory systems, and institutional structures, potentially shaping how farmers perceive and respond to agronomic challenges and opportunities. Understanding these biogeographic and cultural dimensions is therefore essential for interpreting spatial variation in land management and for developing regionally adapted agricultural strategies.

Figure 2: The biogeographical landscape zones of Switzerland with the main linguistic borders listed - German (DE), French (FR), Italian (IT) and Romansh (RM). The map is based on data from the Federal Office for the Environment and the Federal Statistical Office of Switzerland.

1.3 Switzerland's payment schemes

Farmer's behaviour is strongly linked to specific national agricultural policy framework and its soil-related incentive schemes. Within this section we give an overview of the Swiss public schemes, followed by the soil health schemes in Switzerland.

Overview of payment schemes

Swiss agriculture operates within a distinct policy framework, whereby farms are supported financially to a high degree by the Federal Government directly via direct subsidies (known as direct payments) as well as indirectly via border regulations targeting the import and export of agricultural products (Federal Office of Agriculture, 2023a; Huber, 2022; Huber et al., 2023).

Farmers must apply annually for direct payments. A similar mechanism to cross compliance under the Common Agricultural Policy of the EU applies in Switzerland, named proof of ecological performance (German acronym ÖLN). This prerequisite defines a minimum set of ecological requirements and covers elements such as a balanced nutrient management plan, crop rotation and soil conservation measures, minimum share of ecological focus areas, restricted use of plant protection products, and compliance with animal welfare standards where relevant (Federal Office of Agriculture, 2023b). Provided the proof is fulfilled, which is the case for 98% of Swiss farmers (AGRIDEA, 2023), they can apply for payments structured around five key pillars, each designed to support sustainable agricultural development while addressing specific policy objectives (Figure 3). These pillars serve as the foundation of the country's agricultural subsidy framework and guide the allocation of financial support to farms.

Figure 3: Swiss subsidy scheme with the 5 main contribution pillars in green. The proof of ecological performance must be fulfilled as a basic requirement for receiving direct payments.

Farmers can then for example receive “cultural landscape contributions” and “food security contributions” – an equivalent of the CAP Pillar 1 area-based payments. Due to the diverging landscape prevalent across Switzerland, it is important to note that Swiss area based agricultural support payments are also graduated across the distinct agricultural zones (see Figure 2). However, farmers may also enrol for further mainly action-based schemes termed “production system”, “landscape quality” and “biodiversity” contributions, which require that farmers undertake additional practices and meet additional criteria. These schemes are akin to the Agri-environmental schemes under the CAP Pillar 2. All farms that fulfil the corresponding criteria receive the associated payments.

In 2023, approximately CHF 2.79 billion were allocated as direct payments to Switzerland’s agricultural sector, representing on average 28% of farmers’ income (Agrarbericht, 2024; OECD, 2023). In comparison, the average share of subsidies in agricultural income across EU countries is about 23%, with considerable variation between member states—ranging from as low as 8% in the Netherlands and Malta to 45% in Estonia and Slovakia (European Commission, 2025). This underlines the strong role of public support in the economic viability of Swiss farming, especially in light of its topographical and ecological constraints.

Swiss national soil health schemes

Switzerland launched its own national soil strategy in 2020, setting eight targets for agriculture, including the reduction of soil compaction, prevention of soil degradation from erosion, minimising soil organic matter loss and avoiding soil biodiversity loss (Federal Office for the Environment, 2020).

The Swiss Federal Office of Agriculture (FOAG) introduced in 2023 two subsidy schemes within the production system contribution pillar directly targeting soil health. These include the reduced tillage scheme (CHF 250/ha enrolled) and the continuous soil cover scheme (CHF 200/ha enrolled) (Federal Office of Agriculture, 2024). Additionally, several core concepts of sustainable soil management are a statutory minimum requirement for receiving direct payments such as appropriately diversified crop rotations (F. Federal Office of Agriculture, 2023). However, many beneficial soil management practices were not directly subsidised in Switzerland at the time of our survey.

Table 1 provides a broader overview of the national direct payment schemes relevant to soil health and management. These initiatives play a crucial role in advancing soil health and supporting the transition towards more sustainable farming systems in Switzerland. The table also indicates how these payment schemes relate to the number and proportion of farms covered by the survey. Detailed information on the survey's design, methodology, and implementation is presented in Chapter 1.4 and the subsequent sections.

Table 1: Overview of key national direct payment schemes surveyed among Swiss farmers, highlighting their financial incentives, objectives, and areas of focus.

National Direct Payment Scheme	Payment Type	Payment Rate	Survey Participants Enrolled (n responses)	Share in survey sample (% responses)
Contribution for Organic Farming	Action Based	CHF 1200 / ha *	471	17.20%
Contribution for Maintaining Adequate Soil Cover	Action Based	CHF 200 / ha	2008	73.31%
Contribution for Reduced Tillage	Action Based	CHF 250 / ha	1591	58.09%
Contribution for Renunciation of Herbicides	Action Based	CHF 250 / ha †	1195	43.63%
Contribution for Renunciation of Plant Protection Products	Action Based	CHF 400 / ha †	1451	52.98%
Contribution for the Efficient Use of Nitrogen	Action Based	CHF 100 / ha	1079	39.39%

Notes: * The payment rate is differentiated by land type - we only report the rate for arable land here. † The payment rate is differentiated in two levels by crop - we only report the rate for bread wheat here. The exact requirements and payment rates are well described by the Federal Office of Agriculture (FOAG) - for more information consult the [FOAG webpage](#).

Swiss private, public and hybrid soil health business models

In addition to national direct payment schemes, a range of private, public, and hybrid initiatives exist in Switzerland aimed at enhancing soil health and fostering climate-friendly agricultural practices (*Table 2*). These initiatives can be understood as business models, as defined by Archetype 6 in D4.1, and are often voluntarily implemented by farmers or farmer-led associations and are typically regionally focused. Financing can originate from diverse sources, as for example cantonal governments, private banks or foundations. The table also indicates how these business models relate to the number and proportion of farms covered by the survey. Detailed information on the survey's design, methodology, and implementation is presented in Chapter 1.4 and the subsequent sections.

Table 2: Overview of private, public and hybrid soil health business models available to Swiss farmers, highlighting their financial incentives, objectives, and areas of focus.

Business Model Name	Project Type	Time Frame	Geographic Scope	Survey Participants Enrolled (n responses)	Share in Survey Sample (% responses)	Info
Klimaschutz durch Humusaufbau (Living Lab 2 of InBestSoil)	Public-Private	2022-2027	Canton Basel Landschaft	13	0.47%	Link
Résulterre	Public	2024-2029	Canton Genève	6	0.22%	Link
Klimaneutrale Landwirtschaft Graubünden	Public	2021-2030	Canton Graubünden	5	0.18%	Link
Humusbewirtschaftung in der Landwirtschaft	Public (Resource Project)	2017-2025	Canton Solothurn	50	1.83%	Link
Progrès Sol	Public	2017-2021	Canton Vaud	6	0.22%	Link
RISC: Réflexion Innovation Soutien Climat	Public (Resource Project)	2022-2029	Canton Vaud	21	0.77%	Link
AgroCO2ncept	Public (Resource Project)	2016-2024	Flaachtal Region in Canton Zürich	5	0.18%	Link
KlimaStaR Milch	Public (Resource Project)	2022-2029	National but focus region in Central Switzerland, Canton Aargau and Bern	14	0.51%	Link
Agro4esterie	Public (Resource Project)	2020-2027	Canton Bern, Genève, Jura, Neuchâtel and Vaud	18	0.66%	Link
Bodenverbesserung Seeland	Public (Resource Project)	2019-2026	Seeland Region in Canton Bern and Fribourg	11	0.40%	Link
Terres Vivantes	Public (Resource Project)	2019-2026	Jura Region in Canton Bern and Jura	20	0.73%	Link

Note: Other projects were also included in the survey, but we only present here the projects directly related to climate and soil health with several responses in the survey ≥ 3 . Additional information on the resources projects listed here as well as others covering different themes can be found on the [FOAG Ressourcenprogramm webpage](#).

One example of a public–private business model presented in more detail here is Living Lab 2 within Work Package 3 (WP3) of the InBestSoil project. This Living Lab, titled “Klimaschutz durch Humusaufbau” (which translates to Climate Protection through Organic Matter Build-up), focuses on enhancing soil organic matter to contribute to climate mitigation. The Living Lab 2 is a network of 13 Living Lab farms that has been established to test, implement, and demonstrate innovative carbon farming practices under real-world conditions. These Living Labs provide a practical framework for validating soil health measures and carbon sequestration strategies, while also serving as a platform for farmer engagement and knowledge exchange.

Farmers of the Living Lab 2 receive payments from the cantonal bank in Baseland based on the amount of additional carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e) sequestered in their soils. The scheme provides a financial incentive of 100 CHF per tonne of CO₂e stored, verified through soil sampling and monitoring over time. In the pilot region of Basel-Landschaft, approximately 1,100 hectares are enrolled under this business model (Ebenrain, 2020).

By linking payments directly to measurable carbon sequestration outcomes, the living lab aims to deliver tangible climate benefits while simultaneously improving soil fertility and farm resilience. The business model operates as a collaboration between farmers, regional authorities, and private partners, ensuring both scientific monitoring and practical feasibility on the ground. Please refer to the outputs of WP3 for more information.

1.4 Survey on soil health

Initially, the survey targeted farms participating in the carbon farming initiative “Klimaschutz durch Humusaufbau” in the canton of Basel-Landschaft, as well as non-participating farms within the same canton. Nevertheless, the scope of the survey was expanded to include farms across the entire country, thereby encompassing those not involved in Living Lab 2 and addressing a broader range of soil health practices. Accordingly, the survey was designed to gather detailed information on arable farming practices in Switzerland during the 2022/23 growing season, with particular emphasis on understanding the decision-making processes that underpin soil management practice choice for improved soil health. Rather than limiting itself to basic farm characteristics or structural descriptors, the survey aimed to explore the broader behavioural, social, and agronomic context in which farmers operate. By capturing aspects such as personal motivations, perceptions, information sources, and peer influences, the survey sought to provide a more holistic view of the factors shaping agricultural management strategies. It also did not aim for gathering data on isolated practices, but as bundles of practices, which can lead to sustainability transitions as defined by business model archetype 6 in D4.1. The structure and rationale behind the survey design are described in the following section.

Survey design and content

The uptake of sustainable agricultural practices is often associated with structural characteristics such as farm size, labour availability, or participation in agri-environmental schemes. However, these factors alone provide only a partial explanation for farmers' management decisions. Evidence across various contexts suggests that there is no uniform set of determinants that reliably predicts adoption behaviour (Weersink and Fulton, 2020). Rather, decision-making is embedded in specific local realities and shaped by a combination of economic conditions, social relationships, and individual psychological factors (Pannell and Zilberman, 2020).

To account for this complexity, the survey was designed to capture a broader range of influences on soil management, going beyond structural variables. It included questions on farmers' individual priorities, their perception of their own competencies and their long-term objectives. Other dimensions covered exposure to peer practices, participation in advisory and training services, and use of different information channels. These elements are crucial for understanding decision-making processes, given that farmers operate within social networks and are influenced by their values, risk perceptions, and openness to innovation. Financial incentives alone cannot fully explain behaviour; cognitive and motivational factors are equally important. The resulting dataset enables a differentiated analysis of the factors that influence decisions relevant to soil health. By incorporating these variables, the study contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the behavioural underpinnings of sustainable soil management and the adoption of soil health business models, supporting the development of more targeted agricultural policy instruments.

The survey instrument is available in German, French and English. Its final version was developed over a one-year period, involving three external consultation rounds with stakeholders, internal expert reviews and pilot testing with farmers. All participants were required to provide informed consent by confirming their participation via a tick box on the online form. A separate consent checkbox was used to confirm agreement to link their responses to secondary geographic information. The survey was only activated for respondents once both consents had been given. To incentivise participation in the survey we offered the opportunity to enrol in a lottery of 100 supermarket vouchers worth CHF 150 each and the option to receive a personalised results report comparing the farmers' answers to the answers of other similar farms (see chapter 3 for further details).

The structure of the questionnaire remained the same for all respondents. Questions appeared in a predefined order and conditional logic was only applied to filter out inapplicable follow-up items based on previous answers. The full questionnaire contained 57 questions, including all sub-items. The median completion time was 23 minutes.

The survey design was based on earlier national studies on agricultural practices in Switzerland (Kreft et al., 2021; Möhring and Finger, 2022; Späti et al., 2022; Zachmann et al., 2023a, 2023b). It included modules on farm characteristics and participation in soil-related programmes, to assess engagement with public incentives and voluntary schemes. Demographic data were collected to explore the role of personal attributes in management decisions. Questions relating to management practices were developed in close collaboration with soil science and agricultural extension experts and were validated through a review of relevant literature. Additional sections gathered data on milling wheat production and input use, enabling productivity outcomes to be analysed in relation to soil management. Information on structural features such as location, tenure and farm type was collected to provide context for understanding environmental and institutional constraints. Emphasis was placed on behavioural variables, including information-seeking behaviour, risk perceptions and individual aspirations, to capture the cognitive and motivational dimensions of farmer decision-making. The following section describes the variables examined within each thematic block:

Demographic details (Primary dataset columns B-H)

Age, duration farm responsibility, gender, full time equivalent and whether the farm succession is already secured.

Participation in soil health programmes (Primary dataset columns H-S)

Organic farming support, soil cover scheme, reduced tillage scheme, herbicide-free farming scheme, pesticide-free farming scheme, efficient fertilizer use, wider row planting, beneficial insect strip, precision application, cantonal soil health support, cantonal input reduction support, cantonal investment and equipment support.

Management Practices (Primary dataset columns T-CA)

An overview of all management practices addressed in the survey, including their descriptions and the typical machinery used, is provided in *Table 3*. Farmers were asked about their knowledge about the practices, the application as well as the frequency of application within the last 10 years and whether they know other farmers that use the practice. The practices covered by our survey target the improvement of soil health and were selected based on the input of soil scientists and agricultural extension workers based in Switzerland.

Milling Wheat Production (Wheat dataset columns B-M)

Production standard, hectares of milling wheat grown, yield milling wheat, yield milling wheat over last five seasons, quantity synthetic fertiliser, quantity organic fertiliser, sowing density, number of biostimulant treatments, number of herbicide treatments, number of fungicide treatments, number of insecticide treatments and number of plant growth regulator treatments.

Structural Farm Characteristics (Primary dataset columns CD-CP)

Family members employed, farm focus (arable, livestock, permanent crop, others), full time or part-time farm, percentage of rented land, whether the soil has been assessed and a soil management plan exists.

Training and Advice (Primary dataset columns CQ-CZ)

Advice agricultural adviser, advice agricultural retailer, advice cantonal or national institution, consult other farmers, consult social media channels, consult publications or webpages, participation equipment demonstration, participation farmer discussion or training group, participation farm demonstration, participation course.

Behavioural and Attitudinal Factors (Primary dataset columns DA-EK)

Respondents' self-assessment of their perceived influence of weather on crop production and ambitiousness of self-set production goals.

Respondents' self-assessment of their willingness to take risks in the domains of;
Agricultural production, investment in agricultural technology and crop protection.

Respondents' self-assessment of their confidence in being able to;
Find solutions to arable production challenges and achieve production goals by harvest end.

The respondents self-reported importance of the following aspects in decision making;
Maximizing yields, minimizing input costs, minimizing time or labour requirements, minimizing production risks, minimizing farm exposure to weeds or pests or diseases, adapting to weather patterns, adapting to farmland conditions, improving soil health or structure or fertility, improving biodiversity, minimizing environmental impact, expanding farm land, adapting to crop market developments, adapting to changes in direct payment rates or regulations, seeking professional agronomic, seeking casual advice from friends or colleagues and seeking peer approval.

Table 3. Overview of management practices included in the survey, with descriptions and typical machinery used.

Management practice	Description	Typical machinery used
Mulch Tillage	A non-inversion tillage method involving shallow (5-10cm depth) cultivations. The whole soil surface is cultivated, and crop residues are incorporated into the soil surface.(Hegglin et al., 2014; Morris et al., 2010)	- Wide variety of equipment used: - Tined cultivator or disc harrow - Shallow/chisel plough - Rotary harrow
Strip Tillage	A non-inversion tillage method that involves tilling only narrow strips where crops will be planted, leaving the rest of the soil undisturbed.(Hegglin et al., 2014; Morris et al., 2010)	- Specialised seed drill/strip planter

Zero Tillage	A non-inversion crop establishment method (also known as no-till or direct drilling). Zero-Tillage minimises soil disturbance to only directly where the seed is planted.(Hegglin et al., 2014; Morris et al., 2010)	- Specialised direct seeding machines
Contour Farming	Planting crops along natural land contours to minimize soil erosion and runoff, especially on slopes (also known as contour-parallel cultivation).	- Standard equipment (adapted to slope contour)
Deep non-INVERSION tillage	A deep non-inversion tillage treatment for mechanically loosening soil below the usual tillage depth to address compaction or improve drainage, without disturbing the soil surface.(Morris et al., 2010)	- Subsoiler
Controlled Traffic Farming	Operating all machinery for several years only on designated tramlines to minimise soil compaction in non-trafficked areas	- GPS-controlled machines (e.g., seeders and sprayers) - Implements of the same working width
Stubble mulching	Mechanical treatment to chop and distribute crop residues (e.g. stubble) to aid the breakdown of crop residues and aid weed/pest control.	- Mulcher - Mower/topper
Under-sowing of main crop	Planting secondary crops under the primary crop to improve soil cover and suppress weeds.(Hedrich et al., 2024; Niggli et al., 2024)	- Spreader - Specialised or adapted standard seeding technology
Sowing catch crops or green manures	Planting crops within crop rotation to prevent nutrient loss, improve soil structure, and add organic matter. Seed mixtures can be designed for different purposes.(Bernier et al., 2013; Hedrich et al., 2024; Niggli et al., 2024)	- Specialised or adapted standard seeding technology - Could be performed e.g. alongside subsoiling
Application of biochar	Adding charcoal-like material to soil to improve water retention, nutrient holding capacity, and carbon sequestration.	- Manure spreaders with adapted spreading attachments - Specialised spreading technology
Application of compost	Enriching soil with rotted organic material produced from plant material and to boost fertility.(Niggli et al., 2024)	- Manure spreaders with adapted spreading attachments
Soil condition tests	Performing simple tests, like spade sampling, to check if the soil is firm and dry enough to avoid damage before driven on.(Bernier et al., 2013)	- Spade sampling tools

Response rate and data quality

Prior to the full survey launch, we conducted a pilot survey which was sent out to a random sample of 1% of eligible farms (150 farms from 15,023). The pilot survey was conducted to test whether all the technical details work as; that we can send out the emails in bigger batches, that the farmers receive the email and are feasible to start as well as finish the survey and that the questions asked within the survey are clear. The pilot survey launched on 30th November 2023.

As the pilot survey was successful, we started the official survey on the 6 December 2023, and closed on 31 January 2024, following a response window of nearly two months. During this period, we received 2,728 complete responses which results in a response rate of 18.2%. This rate aligns well with, or even exceeds, those observed in comparable agricultural surveys conducted in Switzerland (Kreft et al., 2021; Möhring and Finger, 2022; Späti et al., 2022; Zachmann et al., 2023a, 2023b). 779 participants completed the survey only partially, which results in a completion rate of 77.2% among those who began it (3,515 initiated vs. 2,728 completed), which is consistent with similar Swiss studies. Eight entries were excluded from the dataset due to missing or invalid responses. Exclusions were also applied in cases where respondents indicated they were not involved in any on-farm decision-making. Responding farms represent a wide range of agricultural regions and include both German- and French-speaking parts of Switzerland. The Italian-speaking region was excluded from the analysis, as its agricultural conditions and practices differ markedly from those of other regions, and the number of eligible farms that met our survey criteria from that area was insufficient for inclusion. Figure 4 illustrates the spatial distribution of the farms that participated in the survey.

Figure 4: Geographical distribution of all farms that both received a survey invitation and fully completed the survey.

Note: Most farms are concentrated in valley zones, where arable farming is most viable due to favourable environmental conditions. The grey lines outline the cantons, providing a spatial reference for orientation.

Data cleaning

To reduce input errors already during the data collection, the survey interface was designed to restrict entries to predefined response options or plausible numerical ranges wherever possible. For variables where such restrictions were not technically feasible—such as free-text fields or open numerical inputs—systematic cleaning procedures were carried out after data collection. These procedures addressed missing data, logical inconsistencies, and extreme values. Values considered implausible or clear outliers were either adjusted based on related variables or removed when no reliable correction could be inferred. This cleaning process was applied to variables including plant protection product treatments, yield, sowing density, labour input, and demographic information.

To provide an example of our approach (note all processing codes are available in the supplementary material which outline these decisions on a line-by-line basis), please consider the following: when a value of 48 appeared in the SAK (Full time equivalent) column but was inconsistent with the corresponding farm size, the value was adjusted to 4.8 using information from another related variable. A similar logic was applied to date-of-birth entries; for instance, if a birth year was entered as "60" instead of a full four-digit year (e.g., 1960), and the respondent reported 40 years of farming experience, the birth year was corrected to 1960 based on internal

consistency. When no reliable correction was possible, the value was set to 'NA' (Not Available) to denote missing information.

To ensure the anonymity of participants, precise geographic identifiers were removed, and continuous variables such as age and years of farming experience were grouped into categorical variables (e.g., age group, years experience_group). No randomisation was applied to the dataset. Additionally, in the case of linked secondary datasets, steps were taken to prevent indirect identification by rounding numeric variables to the nearest whole number. Processing scripts for these anonymisation steps are also provided in the supplementary documentation.

Datasets

The data consists of one main dataset and two supplementary datasets. All data and codes are available for download (Rees et al., 2025). Each dataset has columns representing variables (see the codebook for an elaboration of these variables), with each row corresponding to an individual farm.

The main survey dataset “Primary_Data” provides comprehensive information on demographic details, participation in soil health programmes, management practice adoption and knowledge, structural farm characteristics, training and advice, behavioural and attitudinal factors. The supplementary datasets can be linked to the main dataset via a common key variable (“survey_id” - column A in excel), which assigns a unique identifier to each participating farm and is consistently present across all three datasets. The supplementary dataset “Wheat_Data” includes the same farms as the main dataset, but with supplementary data for only those that grew milling wheat in the 2022/2023 farming season. To enhance the contextual understanding of agricultural practices across Switzerland, we integrated an additional dataset retrieved from publicly available geospatial data (Geodienste, 2024). This platform provides updated information on land use at the cantonal level. The incorporation of this secondary data is essential for placing our findings within a broader spatial and agricultural context. The dataset is called “Linked_Secondary_Data” and includes any spatial and meteorological data that we did not collect via our survey but were able to link to the farm via the farm ID number.

Additionally, a PDF document of the complete survey questionnaire used to collect the data is included, available in English, German and French. Additionally, a PDF document of the complete survey questionnaire used to collect the data is included, available in English, German and French. The R scripts in the repository include a quality check script to validate data consistency. However, due to anonymity concerns, exact farm locations are not provided. As a result, scripts that replicate visualisations, such as spatial distributions of farms are not included.

Data validation

To further assess the representativeness of our sample, we compare descriptive farm structural statistics of all farms that were contacted during our survey campaign with comparable survey conducted in Switzerland *Table 4*.

Table 4: Comparison with similar datasets

Variable	Rees et al. 2025 (Data Presented)	Möhring et al 2022 49	Späti et al. 2022 48	Kreft et al 2024 55
Share Rented (%)	37.50 (28.67)	34.94 (28.87)		
Labour Units (full time equivalents)	2.36 (4.40)	1.68 (1.18)	1.86 (2.14)	
Manager Age (years)	47.54 (10.28)	47.08 (9.37)	46.50 (10.37)	49.03 (10.13)
Female (% Yes)	5.06			6.9
French Speaking (% Yes)	22.62	21.9		24.34
Valley Zone (% Yes)	79.18		76.56	
Organic (% Yes)	16.14*		12.92	25.35
Integrated Production (% Yes)	47.90*	100		40.65*
Reduced Tillage Scheme Enrollment (% Yes)	58.14	59.19 †		47.68
Final Number of Usable Responses (No.)	2,728	1,105	418	797
Response Rate (Usable % of asked)	18.16	23.27	8.74	

Notes: A table of descriptive statistics from the here presented dataset versus the three contemporary survey datasets that focused on arable farming in Switzerland. Namely those of Möhring et al. (2022), conducted in 2019, Späti et al. (2022) conducted in 2021 and Kreft et al. (2024), conducted in 2024. These descriptive statistics are also shown alongside general statistics of the entire agricultural sector - including all farm types - of Switzerland from the Federal Office of Statistics for the year 2023.

Chapter 2 – Ex-post impact assessment of soil health improving business models in agriculture¹.

2.1 Conceptual Framework:

From an econometric perspective, analysing the adoption of individual practices in isolation or participation in Agri-environmental schemes – both in binary or continuous terms – leads to a great deal of information loss relating both to the decision-making process and to the possible outcomes of adopted practice combinations by a highly heterogeneous group of actors working under different production conditions and production constraints. This potentially biases the estimation of the impact of such measures - especially if they are generalised to practices - on aspects such as productivity and efficiency. Most soil health beneficial agricultural practices are not performed in isolation but rather in bundles, whereby numerous different practices can be implemented together to different extents and in different combinations (Alskaf et al., 2020; Bijttebier et al., 2018; Canales et al., 2020; Carlisle, 2016; Jaworski et al., 2024). This results ultimately in the creation of viable business models for sustainability transitions. The adoption and mix of practices is largely self-selected by the farm manager on the basis of many varying factors specific to the farm manager and farming situation (Figure 5) (Dessart et al., 2019; Schaub et al., 2023; Wuepper et al., 2023). As many practices are not direct substitutes or complements, different combinations have different modes of action and heterogeneous impact potentials.

The most common approach in the productivity and efficiency literature for analysing ex-post the impacts of environmentally beneficial agricultural production practices is to look at the adoption of agri-environmental schemes (or participation in agri-environmental subsidies) rather than the adoption of explicit combinations of practices. This offers methodological benefits, such as exposure to uniform regulations and minimal area enrolment levels, that make controlling for selection bias simpler (e.g. due to a binary treatment variable). However, looking only at scheme enrolment does not fully capture this heterogeneity of the practices, their uptake extent, length of adoption or their adoption combinations. The extent and combination of production practices adopted by the farm also has important implications on the input usage – not just the output – as certain practices, such as reduced tillage for example, may rely more heavily on inputs of synthetic crop protection inputs. Therefore, looking just at the binary adoption of agri-environmental schemes would also not sufficiently account for the heterogeneity of factors and production constraints impacting input decisions.

¹ This analysis, and earlier versions of it, have already been presented at a number of academic conferences and will also be published in the form of a scientific journal article. See Chapter 3, section 3 for further details on the presentations given and accessing previous versions of this analysis.

Figure 5: Visualisation of conceptual framework (black factors are under the control of the farmer)

This has several key implications that we highlight and address in our analysis by looking at heterogeneous arable soil management practice adoption, instead of participation in agri-environmental schemes or carbon farming initiatives, that benefit soil health. Firstly, not all practices are subsidised, and farmers can do the practices irrespective of the enrolment in government schemes or carbon farming projects. Secondly, farmers may adopt the practices more, or less, intensely than the schemes require as a minimum, and may then be classed wrongly as either an adopter or non-adopter of soil health beneficial practices. For example, in the case of the reduced tillage scheme, a farmer may adopt zero tillage on 100% of the arable land instead of the minimum of 60% of land under mulch tillage necessary to qualify for the payment. A final complication is that some schemes were introduced later than when farmers voluntarily adopted the practices. For example, the reduced tillage scheme in its current form existed since 2023, with its predecessor scheme being established several years before as a resource-use efficiency scheme. See Table 2 above.

Aims and Assumptions:

Our research question centres around analysing how the adoption of arable soil management practices – in terms of bundles for sustainability transitions and business model creation (see Archetype 6 of Deliverable 4.1) as well as with emphasis on improving soil health - also affect the productivity and efficiency of milling wheat production. Whilst acknowledging the issues discussed in the previous section, we propose the following approach to tackle our research aims. Firstly, we aimed to define an arable soil management index that describes the heterogeneous arable soil management strategies employed by farmers in our above presented survey dataset that allows clear comparison across farms. The arable soil management index we created closely follows the cover and management factor (C-Factor) of the universal soil loss equation to model the degree to which any given farm has a production strategy aligned with soil health maintenance and promotion.

Secondly, we aim to model heterogeneous soil management strategies relate to both productivity and efficiency from both an input and output orientation. In the empirical strategy below, we elaborate on how we addressed

these aims empirically, but before explaining this we first highlight our four finer grained conceptual assumptions about how farmers make decisions that governed the selection of our empirical approach:

Assumption 1: On average, farmers not only maximise yields but also aim to minimise input usage. We make this assumption given that a) the literature shows that farmers do not exclusively maximise yield or minimise costs and b) in our data we see that, whilst most farmers rank the priority of minimising costs slightly ahead of maximising yields, the ranking of both priorities were generally very close together.

Assumption 2: Farmers maximise yields and minimise inputs at the hectare level, not at the wheat enterprise level. We make this assumption because all the Swiss Federal and Cantonal legal restrictions on input quantities, expected output quantities, as well as the subsidy payment rates, and dissemination materials are all given in values per hectare. Additionally, when farmers compare their performance, this is generally done on a per hectare basis.

Assumption 3: In the short term, inputs such as land and labour are semi-fixed. We observe farmers for one year and given the time required for purchasing or renting additional land and hiring additional labour, it would be unrealistic to assume that farmers can allocate these factors of production with the same fluidity as crop production inputs like fertiliser, seeds and sprays.

Assumption 4: The combination of soil management practices employed and the extent of their use - reflected by the arable soil management index - is not exogenous as farmers self-select into the overall soil management strategy employed on the farm.

2.2 Methods:

In this analysis a key objective is to bring the issue of heterogeneous soil management practice adoption to the very front of our analysis, in terms of quantifying the potential productivity and efficiency implications of varied strategies adopted by farmers. Yet, accounting for the full heterogeneity of practices a farmer may choose presents empirical challenges from the perspective of devising an identification strategy that would enable the calculation of a causal relationship. The chief concerns that would make a causal analysis challenging is the fact that the heterogeneous soil management practice combinations are self-selection by farmers, meaning the “treatments” vary considerably across place, space and time in a non-randomly assigned way. This is due both to heterogeneities in the production conditions experienced by the farmers as well as the heterogeneities inherent within the decision-making process of farmers themselves. On top of identification challenges, parametric approaches to model productivity and efficiency implications (as used in this analysis), require rather strict methodological assumptions in terms of functional form, value of input variables, and the specification of the efficiency orientation (e.g. normally either input or output). Put together, these factors mean that both methodological adaptations and compromises must be found to draw out important policy insights whilst accounting for the selection issue.

We now outline the stages of our empirical strategy that we implemented to answer our research question under the assumptions that we impose on the decision-making process that farmers make when producing milling wheat in Switzerland. To allow us to present empirical examples at each step, we briefly outline the data we used for conducting this analysis. Firstly, we outline how we modelled the adoption intensity of soil health beneficial production practices (section 2.2.1). Secondly, we define how we address the self-selection issue regarding practice adoption intensity via an instrumental variable approach and how productivity and efficiency can be

measures from an input and output orientation contemporaneously via a hyperbolic distance function (section 2.2.2) .

2.2.1. Modelling Heterogeneous Soil Health Practice Adoption:

We created an arable soil management index (SMI_{arable}) that closely follows the management and cover component (C-factor) of the universal soil loss equation. We followed the parametrisation and scaling factors used by (Panagos et al., 2015) and (Auerswald et al., 2021) to calculate the different component scores of the C-factor using the data we collected via the survey, supplemented by data matched from secondary GIS data. These scores cover the cropping composition (C_{crop}), tillage practices ($C_{tillage}$), residue management ($C_{residue}$) and cover crop practices (C_{cover}). Typically, the tillage, residue management and cover cropping components can be combined into a management score ($C_{management}$) such that:

$$SMI_{arable} = C_{crop} * C_{management} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where:

$$C_{management} = C_{tillage} * C_{residue} * C_{cover} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Cropping Component:

To calculate the contribution of the farm's crop rotation (C_{crop}) to the soil management index score we assigned C-factor weights to each arable crop group grown by the farm and then weighted this by the proportion of the crop group in the farm's arable rotation. Such that:

$$C_{crop} = \sum C_{crop(n)} * \% Arable_{crop(n)} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

The crop group, weights assigned and average arable area proportions for calculating the (C_{crop}) are outlined in Table 5 and the spatial pattern of how the participating farms perform is presented in Figure 6. In qualitative terms a lower score relates to a comparatively better performance given that a higher C-factor represents a greater propensity of the crop to degrade the soil.

Table 5. Crop groups and C-factor weights used for calculating the contribution of the farms crop rotation to the arable soil management index.

Crop Group	C-Factor	Average Arable Proportion (%)
Wheat	0.20	24.93 (10.36)
Barley	0.21	7.75 (7.64)
Other Cereals	0.20	5.14 (8.02)
Maize	0.38	15.29 (10.63)
Legumes	0.32	1.91 (4.54)
Potatoes	0.34	2.94 (6.92)
Sugarbeet	0.34	6.35 (8.38)
Oilseed Rape	0.30	9.28 (8.41)

Other Oilseeds	0.32	2.32 (4.87)
Field Vegetables/Berries	0.35	1.82 (6.38)
Temporary Grassland	0.15	20.01 (20.47)
Biodiversity Area*	0.15	1.08 (2.55)
Other	0.50	1.19 (3.75)

Note: *Within the biodiversity area we only count physical areas set aside for biodiversity that are on the arable land. The proportion of land under the biodiversity scheme "cereals in wider rows" is not counted here.

The C_{crop} scaling factors extracted from the scientific literature also mirror the heuristic relationships outlined in the soil beneficial crop rotation advice leaflets available to farmers in Switzerland (Berner et al., 2013; Böhler et al., 2023; Hedrich et al., 2024; Niggli et al., 2024).

Figure 6. A map showing the relative intensity of the crop rotation and its contribution to the arable soil management index.

There is clear geographic clustering of cropping scores across Switzerland which map closely to geographic and meteorological factors - with the highest scores being calculated for the western plateau region of Cantons Fribourg and Bern, as well as the eastern plateau region of Cantons Aargau, Zürich and Thurgau.

Management Component:

The management component of the arable soil index is itself constructed from three components: tillage practices ($C_{tillage}$), residue management ($C_{residue}$) and cover cropping (C_{cover}).

For calculating the tillage component, we follow (Panagos et al., 2015) but extend the index using information from (McKague, 2023) on the four tillage practices measured in the farm survey so that the C-Factor for the different tillage types are tailored to the Swiss case. This results in the following $C_{tillage}$ factors; inversion tillage

= 1.0, mulch tillage = 0.6, strip tillage = 0.25 and zero tillage = 0.25. The contribution of the tillage practices to the management component is thus calculated as:

$$C_{tillage} = (F_{inversion} * 1.0) + (F_{mulchtill} * 0.6) + (F_{striptill} * 0.25) + (F_{zerotill} * 0.25) \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

Where F represents the proportion of the given tillage operation (inversion, mulch etc.) in relation to all the tillage operations carried out on the arable land of the farm such that:

$$F_{inversion} + F_{mulchtill} + F_{striptill} + F_{zerotill} = 1 \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

For the $C_{residue}$ component we directly follow Panagos et al. (2015) by assuming a C-factor associated with residues of 0.88. The $C_{residue}$ is therefore calculated dependent on the proportion of the arable area where straw is retained and mulch-compost is added - labelled as $F_{residues}$:

$$C_{residues} = (0.88 * F_{residues}) + (1 - F_{residues}) \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Finally, for the (C_{cover}) component, we also directly follow Panagos et al. (2015) in assigning a C-factor of 0.80 to the proportion of the arable land where undersowing and cover crops were used - F_{cover} - such that:

$$C_{cover} = (0.80 * F_{cover}) + (1 - F_{cover}) \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

The combined management component as calculated in Equation 2 above is presented in Figure 7 and the overall arable soil management index that combines the crop rotation and management, calculated by Equation 1, is presented in Figure 8. The arable soil management index is the index that we now use to describe the heterogeneity of the arable soil management strategies employed on each farm and model its impact on productivity and efficiency.

Figure 7. A map showing the relative intensity of the soil management practices per farm with relation to its contribution to the arable soil management index.

Figure 8. A map showing the geographic distribution of arable soil management index scores.

2.2.2. Stochastic Frontier Analysis:

To assess the impact of the adoption of a given soil management strategy, the quantities of productive inputs used and the production output of milling wheat we employ stochastic frontier analysis (Coelli et al., 2005; Kumbhakar and Lovell, 2003). The stochastic frontier approach has a long history and has been widely used in the agricultural economics literature for modelling such relationships. Stochastic frontier analysis enables the quantification of technical efficiency (TE_i), which represents the degree to which productive inputs are turned into outputs by a farm. This is advantageous in our estimation case, seeing that it is clear from the agronomic literature that adoption of different soil management strategies could have both (positive and negative) impacts on productivity (the shape of the production frontier) and input use-efficiency (the distance to the production frontier).

$$y_i = \alpha + X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

$$i = 1, \dots, N$$

And:

$$\varepsilon_i = v_i - u_i$$

Such that:

$$TE_i = \exp(-u_i)$$

Under the stochastic frontier framework, observed output is assumed to be a result of a deterministic component – the production frontier – and an error term (ε_i) comprising two distinct parts. One part of the error term (v_i) is the stochastic noise component with a normal distribution centred on a mean of zero which accounts for random production shocks outside of the control of the producer affecting the observed output deviation from the production frontier. The second part of the error term is the inefficiency component (u_i).

To model the milling wheat production technology, we use the variables within Table 5. Our outcome variable (y_i) is the average milling wheat yield in tonnes per hectare that was harvested by each farm in 2023. As stated in our assumptions above, every input is also at the per-hectare application rate due to the fact that farm managers make application decisions, and log the application rates in official statistics, using reference material per-hectare. As this is the case the usual input term of land area is not included as everything is scaled by the milling wheat production area and this term becomes redundant. Therefore, as productive inputs we have first the arable soil management strategy, which acts as a proxy for capital and/or machinery inputs. We then include fertiliser application, which is an aggregated variable of both synthetic fertiliser (e.g. ammonium nitrate, urea) application and organic fertiliser (e.g. manure, slurry) application based on nitrogen content. The next input covers expenditure on plant protection and establishment inputs (e.g. seeds, fungicides, herbicides and plant growth regulators). Lastly, we include the labour availability as the last productive input that can be altered by the farmer. However, in our analysis we assume that labour and the arable soil management strategy are quasi-fixed inputs given that we only observe farms for one production season and the availability of labour and machinery tends to be less liquid over short periods of time compared to variable crop inputs. All inputs and controls are represented by the vector X_i in the equations above.

Besides these inputs that farmers can decide on, we also include several environmental control variables that cover wheat field-specific soil, weather and geographic conditions (Table 6). Lastly, we include a spatial lag of the average milling wheat yield achieved by the 10 neighbouring farms in the preceding 5 wheat production years to mop up unobserved local factors that we cannot control for in our other variables already mentioned, such as local disease pressures and local soil type specificities beyond textural aspects.

Table 6. Main variables used within the frontier estimations as outputs, productive inputs and controls.

Variable Name	Unit	Description	Mean	Standard Deviation
Yield	tonnes/ha	The average milling wheat yield reported by the farm harvested in 2023	6.34	1.07
Arable Soil Management Index	index (0-1)	An index created based on the C-factor equation to model the degree to which the farm produces using an intensive soil management production technology. A higher score represents a more intensive soil management strategy that is in turn more negatively correlated with soil health maintenance and improvement.	0.17	0.05
Fertiliser	kg N/ha	The average application rate of nitrogen fertiliser from both synthetic and organic sources applied to the milling wheat fields.	135.91	33.92
Other Inputs	CHF/ha	The average expenditure on seeds and plant protection products on the milling wheat fields. This is calculated from the sowing density and number of treatments of fungicide, herbicide and plant growth regulators.	353.57	82.80

Labour	FTE/ha	The labour availability for milling wheat production.	0.06	0.03
Clay Content	%	The weighted average soil clay content at a depth of 5-15 cm across the milling wheat fields belonging to the farm.	24.52	5.64
Sand Content	%	The weighted average soil sand content at a depth of 5-15 cm across the milling wheat fields belonging to the farm.	39.97	9.29
Precipitation	mm	The total amount of precipitation during the 12-month milling wheat crop production cycle (September 2022-August 2023) as a weighted average across the milling wheat fields belonging to the farm.	1,000.76	112.47
Temperature	°C	The mean temperature during the 12-month milling wheat crop production cycle (September 2022-August 2023) as a weighted average across the milling wheat fields belonging to the farm.	10.99	0.60
Altitude	m a.s.l.	The weighted average altitude of the milling wheat fields belonging to the farm.	532.32	113.71
Local Historical Average Yield	tonnes/ha (spatial lag)	The weighted average yield reported for the 10 geographically nearest neighbours for the five years preceding the 2022/2023 production year, termed a spatial lag of yield. This is included to account for any omitted variables that are specific to the locality of the farm that might impact production (e.g. other soil characteristics etc.).	6.43	0.44

Note: Each variable was log-transformed when entered in the model. Additionally, the productive inputs of Fertiliser, Other Inputs and Labour were scaled by their geometric means in the models. We provide descriptive statistics of the non-transformed and non-scaled variables for the whole sample in this summary table.

We also include three inefficiency determinants which aim to explain some of the reasoning behind different achieved technical efficiency scores across farms (Table 7). Here we also assume that whilst the arable soil management strategy can influence productivity, it can also influence the efficiency of input allocation for a given input-output relationship. As is common in the productivity literature, we also include the years of farm management experience with the assumption that additional years of management experience are linked with more efficient management. Lastly, we include the milling wheat area here as in the deterministic part of the frontier model all inputs are scaled per hectare and the land component falls away. However, we can include it as an inefficiency determinant under the assumption that a greater area of wheat production is linked with more efficient input allocation per hectare of wheat grown – in effect representing efficiency gains from scale.

Table 7. Variables used within the frontier estimations as inefficiency determinants.

Variable Name	Unit	Description	Mean	Standard Deviation
Arable Soil Management Index	index (0-1)	An index created based on the C-factor equation to model the degree to which the farm produces using an intensive soil management production technology. A higher score represents a more intensive soil management strategy that is in turn more negatively correlated with soil health maintenance and improvement.	0.17	0.05

Management	years	The number of years of experience of the farm manager.	18.58	11.50
Wheat Area	ha	The total number of hectares of the farm that were used for milling wheat production in the 2022/2023 production year.	6.18	5.43

Note: Each variable was log-transformed when entered in the model. We provide descriptive statistics of the non-transformed and non-scaled variables for the whole sample in this summary table.

In many cases within the productivity literature, either an input or output orientation is selected to model the behaviour of the decision-making units. However, this is limited as it assumes that farmers either only actively try to minimise inputs or only actively try to maximise outputs. From the behavioural literature and evidence from the farm survey we conducted (presented in chapter 1) we know that this simplistic framework is not applicable in our case as farmers are actively trying to both minimise inputs and maximise outputs at the same time. On this basis we elected to use a Translog Hyperbolic Distance Function (THDF), as proposed by (Cuesta and Zofío, 2005), instead of a traditional input or output orientation. The THDF allows for the fact that both inputs and outputs can be both minimised and maximised contemporaneously and has been used in the literature to enable the parametric calculation of environmental and eco-efficiency under the stochastic frontier framework (Adenuga et al., 2020; Cuesta et al., 2009).

As a final addition to our estimation strategy, we also allow for the fact that the uptake of beneficial soil management strategies is not exogenous, i.e. the choice of practices, their intensities and combinations is self-selected by the farmer. This is a known phenomenon from the behavioural economics literature but is not frequently dealt with in the production economics literature. Failing to account for the endogenous strategy self-selection of farmers would mean that the coefficients of the main variable of interest (Arable Soil Management Index) would be biased and the real association may be hidden due to the fact that the endogenous Arable Soil Management Index score would be correlated with the error term if no adjustment was made. To do this we follow a similar approach to that proposed by (Karakaplan, 2017) with bespoke model code that allows for endogeneity correction of a continuous input variable, that we developed in collaboration with the R package *sfaR*. The application we present here is one of the first, if not the first of such a combination of model components to address both the endogeneity issue and input/output orientation constraint in a single analysis.

To account for the endogeneity of the arable soil management strategy we embed an instrumental variable approach within a first stage of the modelling process. For the three instruments included to extract the exogenous impact of the arable soil management strategy, we use the spatial lag of the soil management strategy for the 10 nearest farms, the number of years of management and the average slope angle of the wheat fields (Table 8). These variables are strongly correlated with the observed arable soil management strategy on $farm_i$ but are also not correlated with the observed milling wheat yield of $farm_i$, meaning the exclusion restriction holds and that the instruments are strong. Therefore, the only impact of the instruments on the milling wheat yield is via their influence on the soil management strategy selected by the farmer.

Table 8. Instrumental variables used within the endogeneity-corrected frontier to account for self-selection bias.

Variable Name	Unit	Description	Mean	Standard Deviation
Local Arable Soil Management Index	index (spatial lag)	The weighted average arable soil management index score calculated for the 10 geographically nearest neighbours.	0.17	0.02

Management experience	years	The number of years of experience of the farm manager.	18.58	11.50
Slope	%	The weighted average plot slope angle of the milling wheat fields belonging to the farm.	3.66	2.44

Note: Each variable was log-transformed when entered in the model. We provide descriptive statistics of the non-transformed variables for the whole sample in this summary table.

2.3 Results:

In this section we present the results of both, the standard stochastic frontier model without endogeneity correction, alongside the endogeneity-corrected model that takes into account that the arable soil management strategy is self-selected by farmers (Table 9). The productive inputs are also scaled by their geometric average, meaning the coefficient of the first-order terms for Fertiliser, Other Inputs and Labour can be interpreted as elasticities.

In both versions of the model, the productive inputs all have the expected sign and are significantly different from zero at the sample mean ($p < 0.001$). For our key variable of interest - the arable soil management index - we find a slightly negative but non-significant relationship for the model where we do not account for the fact that farmers self-select into their production strategy. However, **when we take account of the endogeneity of the choice of soil management strategy, we find a positive impact on productivity from pursuing a more technologically intensive soil management strategy** that is significant below the $p < 0.05$ level. Additionally, the eta test for the endogeneity of this variable is highly significant, meaning that the endogeneity correction is necessary and therefore the endogeneity corrected model presented in Table 8 is the most appropriate specification of the two (Karakaplan, 2017).

We also include the arable soil management index in the inefficiency determinants. The sign and magnitude of the inefficiency effects are very similar, however, the magnitude of the coefficient of the arable soil management index is slightly larger in the endogeneity corrected model. The significance level is also marginally lower in the endogeneity corrected model ($p < 0.05$ versus $p < 0.1$). The overall result suggests that **having a management strategy that is more intensive is associated with reductions in technical inefficiency** (i.e. gains in efficiency). Moreover, we also see that **a greater degree of farm management experience and farming a greater area of wheat are also associated with reductions in inefficiency**.

When it comes to overall technical efficiency of the wheat producing enterprises analysed above, the mean technical efficiency score reported for the endogeneity corrected model is 0.92 (Table 10). The distribution of technical efficiency scores is rather tightly concentrated and positively skewed (Figure 9). As we use a translog hyperbolic distance function, this means that on average Swiss milling wheat producers can improve their milling wheat output per hectare by 8.70% (1/TE score) whilst simultaneously reducing the use of productive inputs such as fertiliser and other plant protection costs by 8.00% (1-TE score result).

Table 9. Model output for the restricted translog hyperbolic distance function estimates.

	Standard Model	Endogeneity-Corrected Model
<i>Productive inputs</i>		
Intercept	3.832 (0.397)***	3.412 (0.453)***

ln(Arable Soil Management Index)	-0.013 (0.011)	0.096 (0.041) [*]
ln(Fertiliser)	0.147 (0.009) ^{***}	0.148 (0.009) ^{***}
ln(Other Inputs)	0.269 (0.009) ^{***}	0.253 (0.011) ^{***}
ln(Labour)	0.055 (0.004) ^{***}	0.057 (0.005) ^{***}
$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \ln(\text{Fertiliser})^2$	0.035 (0.003) ^{***}	0.034 (0.003) ^{***}
$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \ln(\text{Other Inputs})^2$	-0.041 (0.034)	-0.051 (0.036)
ln(Fertiliser)*ln(Other Inputs)	-0.079 (0.014) ^{***}	-0.074 (0.015) ^{***}
ln(Clay Content)	-0.031 (0.021)	-0.031 (0.023)
ln(Sand Content)	-0.024 (0.016)	-0.026 (0.017)
ln(Precipitation)	0.087 (0.028) ^{**}	0.087 (0.030) ^{**}
ln(Temperature)	-0.179 (0.071) [*]	-0.087 (0.083)
ln(Altitude)	-0.049 (0.019) ^{**}	0.028 (0.034)
ln(Local Historical Average Yield)	0.165 (0.037) ^{***}	0.148 (0.040) ^{***}
<i>Inefficiency determinants</i>		
u (Intercept)	-4.587 (0.454) ^{***}	-4.638 (0.458) ^{***}
u ln(Arable Soil Management Index)	-0.405 (0.216) [*]	-0.436 (0.217) [*]
u Management	-0.011 (0.005) [*]	-0.013 (0.005) ^{**}
u ln(Wheat Area)	-0.300 (0.072) ^{***}	-0.297 (0.072) ^{***}
<i>Model diagnostics</i>		
v (Intercept)	-5.268 (0.093) ^{***}	-5.269 (0.092) ^{***}
zeta ln(Arable Soil Management Index)		-0.115 (0.041) ^{**}
AIC	-2939.470	-1854.946
Num. obs.	1606	1606
Log Likelihood	1488.735	964.473

*Note: Dependent variable is the natural logarithm of milling wheat yield per hectare. The first model presented uses standard SFA and the second model shows the endogeneity corrected model, whereby we take account of the self-selection of soil management strategies by farmers**** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; · $p < 0.1$; zeta indicates the result of the eta test for the endogeneity

Table 10. Technical efficiency and inefficiency scores for the endogeneity-corrected stochastic frontier model

Score	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Median	Maximum
TE	0.92	0.04	0.58	0.93	0.99
E(u ε)	0.08	0.05	0.01	0.07	0.54

Figure 9. Histogram showing the distribution of technical efficiency for the endogeneity corrected stochastic frontier model of milling wheat production per hectare using a restricted translog hyperbolic distance function.

2.4 Discussion:

Our results illustrate clearly the dichotomy of production and environmental outcomes that result from pursuing ever more soil health beneficial management practices. Looking at the results purely from a production standpoint, it would be straightforward to conclude that **performing more intense cultivations**, and not performing cultural practices, **is beneficial for wheat output and also the efficiency of productive input use**. On the other hand, a more rounded interpretation would conclude our findings are a classic illustration of a market failure. If relying only on the market for remuneration of production activities - and in lieu of behavioural/attitudinal differences - decision makers maximise their private benefit and choose the strategies that generate the greatest outputs and greatest efficiency of input use (i.e. greatest conversion of inputs into maximum outputs). In doing so, the private benefit outweighs the public costs - and arguably the long-term private costs as well. **A negative externality is the result because the intensive production strategies incur greater erosion, degradation of soil ecosystem services and compromised soil health.**

This is one of the core challenges associated with greater adoption of more environmentally friendly bundles of farming practices and eventually the creation of related business models, in that doing so comes with likely negative impacts on production when considering yields and input requirements. This is especially the case in the short-term, given that it usually takes several years to get competent in managing a new production strategy as well as realise any - if there are any - economic benefits. It is also difficult for a farmer to detect and/or quantify any environmental benefits over such a period too. However, the reduction in yields and the reduced input use efficiency are detectable and quantifiable for farmers from the start. Much research has shown that farmers tend to be more risk averse and are less willing to adopt a new strategy if the time horizons to a return are longer.

For many farmers, the production risks are too great in comparison to incentive payments, potential input savings and long-term environmental benefits.

Chapter 3 – Dissemination of findings

3.1 Outreach to Farmers

As part of the survey, farmers were offered the option to receive a personalised benchmarking report. This report compared their farm's performance—specifically the number and extent of soil management practices used—to those of similar farms. The goal was to incentivise participation by providing direct, tailored feedback and offering a platform with relevant documents and resources to help address potential issues on arable land.

We opted to do this in a digital format via the creation of a bespoke R-Shiny app that we sent to the 2'001 farmers who requested the benchmarking report. The application is free to view at <https://fibl.shinyapps.io/InBestSoil/>. Each farmer was issued with a unique 15-character token which enabled them to benchmark the answers they gave in the survey against other farms. The application is interactive in that farmers could filter by many different factors – i.e. farm size, geographic area and production system – so that they could compare the results in whatever way they liked.

By developing the benchmarking application, we sought to give farmers actionable insights derived from their own data, enabling them to assess their practices in relation to similar farms (Figure 11), identify potential areas for improvement and eventually business model creation (in line with Archetype 6 of D4.1). Additionally, farmers were provided with helpful tools to expand their expertise in soil health (Figure 12). Development of this benchmarking application began in March 2024, after the end of the survey campaign on the 31st January 2024. The above linked version of the live application was sent via email to the farmers on 11th of June 2024. The farmers were able to provide feedback on the survey and application. While the overall feedback response rate was low, the feedback received was highly positive. Aside from sharing the application with the farmers who participated, we also presented the application to the Swiss Federal Office of Agriculture on 22 October 2024.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the developed personalised benchmarking app.

Note: The farmers had the possibility to access the app with a unique token, with which they could then see their farms performance in comparison to the other farms that took part in the survey. The own performance was marked with a dark green diamond (◆) while the other farms were marked with brown dots (●).

Figure 12: Screenshot of the developed benchmarking app, where farmers were provided with helpful tools to expand their expertise on soil health.

3.2 Outreach to Other Non-science Actors

Several outputs related to policy and practice have been delivered or are planned:

- Presentation of the project and the benchmarking app at the Swiss Federal Office of Agriculture on 22 October 2024;
- Presentation at the Annual Swiss Conference of Agricultural Economists, hosted at the Swiss Federal Office of Agriculture in May 2025;
- [work in progress] Article in the sustainable agriculture magazine “Oekologie & Landbau” (to be released in the December 2025 issue), which is widely read by practitioners and policy-makers in Austria, Germany and Switzerland;
- [work in progress] Policy brief on results-based payments for soil health (to be submitted to Science Policy Forum in December 2025);
- [work in progress] Agrarpolitik Blog – Post(s) foreseen for 2026.

3.3 Academic presentations and papers

We have submitted a data descriptor article to Scientific Data, a journal published by the Nature Portfolio and have made the data available at Zenodo under the DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15488101>.

In accordance with our data-sharing agreement with FOAG, the use of the provided information about farmers was strictly limited within the scope of this project and may not be disclosed to any third party not covered by the agreement. The data are securely stored on FiBL servers in encrypted files and will be retained only for the duration of the project. Upon completion, all personally identifiable contact details will be permanently deleted. Furthermore, the data used in this deliverable has been fully anonymised to safeguard the privacy of participating farmers. Additional steps have been taken to reduce any potential risk of re-identification through survey responses—for instance, sensitive variables such as the age of the farm manager, wheat acreage, or geographic location have been grouped into broader categories or removed completely. As a result, the publicly accessible dataset we provide differs slightly from the version used internally for analysis under the FOAG data agreement.

In addition to the data article and based on the stochastic frontier analysis presented in this deliverable, a journal article is currently being prepared, with the aim of submitting it to the American Journal of Agricultural Economics in September 2025.

To reach a wide scientific audience, presentations were made at three scientific conferences related to various aspects of Deliverable 4.2. These are as follows:

- Biennial conference of the Agricultural Economics Society in Bourdeaux in April 2025;
- Annual Swiss Conference of Agricultural Economists in Bern in May 2025;
- Triennial congress of the European Association of Agricultural Economists in Bonn in August 2025.

Currently, the survey data are also used as part of a PhD Thesis (co-supervised by FiBL and ETH Zurich) and a Master’s Thesis (co-supervised by FiBL and Hohenheim University).

4. Conclusions

This deliverable provides an in-depth ex-post evaluation of business models and soil management strategies designed to enhance soil health, with a special link to the second living lab of the InBestSoil project, i.e. Swiss arable farming systems. By combining detailed survey data from over 2,700 farms with state-of-the-art estimation of production functions, the study uncovers insights into the implications of soil health practices for economic performance - both within and beyond existing policy frameworks.

The Swiss case examined in D4.2 aligns closely with archetype 6 of D4.1: Facilitate Sustainability Transition. Swiss agriculture operates within a strong policy framework in which farms receive direct payments and can enrol in additional action-based schemes that reward sustainable practices such as reduced tillage, soil cover, and improved nutrient management. These policy instruments play a central role in shaping farmers' decisions and supporting the adoption of soil-health practices. This institutional setting reflects a transition-oriented business model in which value is co-created through coordinated action between farmers and policymakers.

From a business model perspective, the value proposition in the Swiss case centres on improving soil health while maintaining farm productivity, supported by national schemes and sustainability-oriented incentives. The value creation and delivery mechanisms are realized through the adoption of soil health practices encouraged by public payments, advisory support, and benchmarking tools that facilitate learning and gradual transition. These mechanisms help address the market failure identified in the Swiss analysis, where individual economic motivations alone are insufficient to motivate long-term soil stewardship.

In terms of value capture, Swiss farmers benefit economically through direct payments and participation in soil-related schemes, which represent a substantial share of farm income. At the same time, they implicitly capture broader value through improved soil resilience, productivity stability, and alignment with long-term sustainability goals. This reflects the transition-oriented logic of Archetype 6, where economic and environmental benefits are generated through policy-supported adoption of sustainable practices.

In terms of concrete results, the analysis reveals that Swiss farmers engage with soil health in diverse and complex ways, often integrating multiple practices and responding to a mixture of incentives, motivations, and constraints. While public subsidies play a significant role in shaping soil management decisions, many farmers implement regenerative practices independent of direct payments, highlighting the importance of individual values, knowledge networks, and local agronomic conditions.

Importantly, the econometric impact estimations demonstrate that **soil health-improving practices come with compromises in terms of productivity and efficiency over the short-term**. When accounting for farmers' self-selection into different soil management strategies, the analysis finds a statistically significant and positive effect, linking a higher intensity of soil management strategies (i.e. less regenerative strategies) to a higher productivity and efficiency in milling wheat production, albeit the magnitude is very small.

The findings underscore a classic policy dilemma: while the environmental benefits of soil health practices are clear and accrue to the public over time, the private incentives for farmers to adopt such practices remain limited in many cases. As such, **this research reinforces the need for well-calibrated policy instruments that align private decision-making with public goals. It also illustrates the value of behavioural and attitudinal insights in designing more effective interventions—highlighting the roles of farmer motivations, peer influence, and perceived risk in driving or hindering adoption and transitions to soil health business models.**

Looking forward, the InBestSoil framework offers a promising foundation for scaling up farmer-centred and evidence-based soil health interventions. Future research should continue to refine the soil management index and explore longitudinal impacts of soil practices on agronomic, economic and ecological outcomes. Moreover, follow-up projects could expand on the interactive tools developed (e.g., the benchmarking app), integrate participatory approaches, and foster living labs to support continuous learning and innovation among farmers and policymakers alike. These steps will be crucial to closing the gap between knowledge and practice, and ensuring that investments in soil health translate into both sustainable agriculture and resilient food systems.

These are key take-ways messages that can inform future decisions on soil health improvements:

- Our analysis shows a trade-off between productivity and soil health, as more intensive soil management strategies (e.g. frequent tillage, limited cover crops) increase wheat yields and input-use efficiency in the short term, but come at the cost of degrading soil health and ecosystem services.
- Farmers tend to choose practices that maximise private economic returns, even if these harm soils in the long run. Without targeted incentives for the creation of soil health business models, the public benefits of healthy soils (erosion control, fertility, biodiversity) are undervalued, leading to underinvestment in sustainable practices.
- The study finds that farmers with more management experience and larger wheat areas achieve higher efficiency, highlighting the role of knowledge, skills, and scale in making soil-friendly strategies viable.

Overall, the Swiss case demonstrates how policy-driven incentives, bench marking and advisory tools can facilitate a gradual sustainability transition in soil management towards business models that can generate long-term soil health benefits. This confirms the relevance of Archetype 6 as a guiding framework for interpreting the Swiss business models and illustrates how macro-level governance structures can enable farmers to integrate soil health into their business strategies.

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Annex I - Task Description

TASK 4.2. EX-POST EVALUATION OF BUSINESS MODELS FOR IMPROVING SOIL HEALTH IN AGRICULTURE (LEADER: FiBL, PARTNERS: LGI; M10-M32).

Using a country-wide case study, Task 4.2 will utilise survey data and ex-post impact evaluation methods to establish causal links between prevailing soil health interventions and observed impacts. For data collection, we will implement online farm surveys among farms in Switzerland that adopted soil health promoting practices (intervention groups) and farms that have not been exposed to these initiatives (control groups). This includes data on practices, farm characteristics and performance. The analysis will test whether existing soil health practices increase farm eco-efficiency alongside other impacts.

A quasi-experimental approach is proposed to compare data from farmers who adopted soil health schemes against data for non-adopters, and, if applicable, also dis-adopters. Statistical matching and reweighting methods (propensity score matching, inverse probability weights, entropy balancing) will be used to minimize the effect of selection bias (Hainmueller, 2012; Hainmueller and Xu, 2013, Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016). The matching and weighting methods mitigate endogenous selection by creating a synthetic control group composed of non-adopting households that are similar to households that adopt concerning the observed farm and householdlevel characteristics. Using more than one technique to control for confounding effects helps to check robustness of results and better understand the implications of method choice.

The research intends to gather information not only on easily observable confounders (farm size, education, etc.), but also on aspects of motivation or risk behaviour. To assess the possible role of omitted unobservable confounders, Oster bounds will be applied (Oster, 2019). As farming systems are usually complex with multiple interactions and non-linearities between various biological, ecological and socioeconomic processes, flexible functional forms might be needed. WP4 may thus resort to recent methods from machine learning that address model uncertainty and efficiently deal with large number of potential explanatory variables to estimate the causal impacts of soil health promoting schemes (Chernozhukov et al., 2017 and 2018).

The primary output variables will capture carbon sequestration, alongside other soil health and environmental impacts, and farm income effects that can materialize through potential compensation schemes or changes in cost structures arising from the implementation of these practices. Indicators will be based on the indicators selected in WP3, where possible. Reduction of environmental pressures together with changes in economic performance will be integrated into one main indicator, namely eco-efficiency. In addition, secondary outcome variables involve changes in yields and resilience. As indicated in the introduction section, adoption of soil health promoting practices can improve yield and support resilience through enhanced soil fertility, reduced soil erosion and lower crop failures. All key outcome indicators can be further refined through initial stakeholder consultations. The output of the task will be an ex-post impact evaluation report (D4.2).

